

SYNTHETIC INSECTICIDES. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF $\alpha\alpha$ -BIS-(ARYL)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -TRICHLORO-*n*-BUTANES

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In the present work the condensations of benzene, chlorobenzene, bromobenzene and naphthalene with butylchloral hydrate have been carried out when in the first three cases the products of the type $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(R-phenyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-*n* butanes (where R=H, Cl and Br respectively) were obtained. The structures of these compounds have been established by first dehydrohalogenating and subsequently oxidising the crude dehydrohalogenated compounds to their respective benzophenones. Dehydrohalogenation and oxidation of the naphthalene condensation product were attempted but without success. Hence, this compound has been provisionally assigned the constitution $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(α -naphthyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ trichloro-*n*-butane.

The discovery by Lauger Muller and Martin (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1944, 27, 897) of the remarkable insecticidal properties of the compound $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(*p*-chlorophenyl)- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethane, popularly known as DDT, has opened a wide field of research in synthetic insecticides. Since then, much work on the synthesis of the analogues of DDT has been carried out with a view to obtaining compounds of possible insecticidal action. Stephenson and Waters (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 339) have synthesised a number of 4:4'-disubstituted derivatives of $\alpha\alpha$ -(diphenyl)- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethane (DT), like 4:4'-dimethyl-DT, 4:4'-diethyl-DT, 4:4'-dibromo-DT, 4:4'-difluoro-DT, 4:4'-dihydroxy-DT and their methyl, ethyl, propyl, butyl ethers, etc. So also the bromal analogues of DDT like $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(*p*-chlorophenyl)- $\beta\beta\beta$ -tribromoethane and $\alpha\alpha$ -bis(*p*-bromophenyl)- $\beta\beta\beta$ -tribromoethane have been synthesised by Cristol and Haller (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 140) and Lauger *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Lauger and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) in their study of insecticidal property and chemical constitution observed that $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(*p*-chlorophenyl)- $\alpha\beta\beta$ -trichloroethane with the grouping

to synthesise compounds by using other halogenated aldehyde instead of chloral so that

the grouping $>CH-C$ present in DDT be replaced by $-C-C-$ For this

purpose butylchloral hydrate was selected so that the condensation products obtained

would have the grouping CH_3-C , and which may possess insecticidal activity.

Reference to literature reveals that so far no work on the condensation of butylchloral hydrate with hydrocarbons and halo-hydrocarbons has been carried out.

In the present work butylchloral hydrate has been condensed with benzene, naphthalene, chlorobenzene and bromobenzene. Butylchloral hydrate, when condensed with chlorobenzene in presence of oleum at 29°-30°, gave $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(*p*-chlorophenyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-*n*-butane (I, R=Cl). The same compound was obtained with chlorosulphonic acid; however, oleum was found to be a better condensing agent. The structure of this compound was proved by dehydrohalogenation and subsequent oxidation of the crude unsaturated compound, when *pp'*-dichlorobenzophenone was obtained.

Similarly, the condensations of benzene and bromobenzene with butylchloral hydrate were carried out when $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(phenyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-*n*-butane (I, R=H) and $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(*p*-bromophenyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-*n*-butane (I, R=Br) respectively were obtained. The structures of these compounds were established in the same way, by degradation through dehydrohalogenation and subsequent oxidation to the respective benzophenones.

Naphthalene, when similarly condensed with butylchloral hydrate, gave a di-condensation product (m.p. 196-98°). All attempts at dehydrohalogenating this compound proved unsuccessful. It may be tentatively suggested that the constitution of the compound is $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(α -naphthyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-*n*-butane (II). The dehydrohalogenation may not be taking place due to steric hindrance exerted by the heavy groups (fused benzene rings) attached on both the sides in position *ortho* to the carbon atoms which are linked to the butylchloral group.

Further work on similar condensations with alkylbenzenes, chloronaphthalenes, phenols and their ethers, etc., is in progress.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Condensation of Butylchloral Hydrate with Chlorobenzene: $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-*n*-butane.—Butylchloral hydrate (30 g.) was taken in a three-necked flask equipped with a mercury seal stirrer, thermometer and a separating funnel which contained oleum (5%, 100 g). About 10 g. of oleum (24%) were added to butylchloral hydrate with stirring to remove water of the hydrate, indication being no lowering of temperature even if more oleum were added. It was then allowed to attain room temperature (29°-31°) and chlorobenzene (38.5 g.) was added followed by a slow addition of oleum with stirring, controlling the temperature at 29°-31°, by external cooling. The stirring was continued for 5 hours in all. The reaction mixture was kept overnight and next day it was poured over crushed ice when yellowish brown pasty product was obtained. This was washed well with cold and then boiling water.

After two crystallisations from acetic acid needles were obtained, m.p. 81°, yield 10 g. (Found: Cl, 46.3. $C_{18}H_{13}Cl_2$ requires Cl, 46.3 per cent). *Tetranitro derivative*, m.p. 241-42°. (Found: N, 9.6. $C_{18}H_5O_8N_4Cl_2$ requires N, 9.9 per cent).

The same condensation was also carried out though less conveniently using chloro-sulphonic acid (45 g.) when, after four crystallisations, pure product (m.p. 81°) was obtained.

Dehydrohalogenation of α -bis-(p-Chlorophenyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-n-butane and Oxidation of the crude Dehydrohalogenated Compound.—Pure compound (2 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) and to this was added potassium hydroxide (2 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of water. This was refluxed on a water-bath for half an hour. The alcohol was then removed and the residue was extracted with ether, the extract washed, dried and the ether evaporated. Yellowish paste was isolated which could not be crystallised, and hence was directly subjected to oxidation.

The unsaturated compound obtained as above (1.5 g.) was dissolved in acetone and potassium permanganate (about 30 g.) was added. The whole mixture was then heated on a water-bath for about an hour. Sulphur dioxide was then passed to dissolve the precipitated manganese dioxide. It was then extracted with ether, the extract washed, dried and the ether removed. The product after crystallisation from alcohol was found to be *pp'*-dichlorobenzophenone, m.p. 142-44° (Grummitt, Buck and Jenkins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 155, record m.p. 143-44°). The mixed melting point of this with *pp'*-dichlorobenzophenone obtained from DDT was not depressed.

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones* gave bright red crystals, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen from *pp'*-dichlorobenzophenone, 230°. (Found: N, 13.1 $C_{18}H_{13}O_4N_4Cl_2$ requires N, 13.1 per cent).

Condensation of Butylchloral Hydrate with Bromobenzene: α -bis-(p-Bromophenyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-n-butane.—Butylchloral hydrate (24 g.) was condensed with bromobenzene (47.1 g., 20% excess) in presence of oleum (5%, 100 g.) at 45°, the stirring being continued for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was then poured over ice, when a pasty product was obtained. This was washed as in the previous case and subjected to steam-distillation when the unreacted substances passed over. The product that remained was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 97-99°, yield 20 g. (Found: Cl, 21.6; Br, 36.3. $C_{18}H_{13}Cl_3Br_2$ requires Cl, 22.5; Br, 33.9 per cent).

The crude dehydrohalogenated product, obtained from the above compound (2 g.) after refluxing it with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (2 g.) was directly oxidised by boiling with chromic acid (2 g.) in acetic acid for 2 hours. It was diluted, neutralised with sodium bicarbonate, extracted with ether and the extract dried. On removal of ether *pp'*-dibromobenzophenone (m.p. 172°) was obtained (Hoffmann, *Annalen*, 1891, 264, 163, records m.p. 172-73°). Oxime, m.p. 145-49° (Hoffmann, *loc cit.*, m.p. 145-49°).

Condensation of Butylchloral Hydrate with Benzene: α -bis-(Phenyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-n-butane.—Butylchloral hydrate (24 g.) was condensed with benzene (25 g.) in presence of oleum (4%, 200 g.) at 29°-31° for 6 hours. This was then poured over ice when the solid product was obtained. This was washed well with water and crys

tallised from alcohol when white needles (yield 18 g.), m.p. 83-84°, were obtained. (Found : Cl, 33.9. $C_{10}H_{10}Cl_2$ requires Cl, 33.9 per cent).

The crude product obtained on dehydrohalogenation of the above compound (2 g.) with alcoholic potassium hydroxide was oxidised by refluxing with chromic acid (4 g.) in acetic acid for 4 hours. On working up a yellowish liquid was isolated. This may be the labile form of benzophenone, m.p. 26-26.5° (Zincke, *Annalen*, 1871, 189, 378; 381).

2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen from benzophenone, 233-34° (Found : N, 15.2. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4N_4$ requires N, 15.4 per cent).

Condensation of Butylchloral Hydrate with Naphthalene : $\alpha\alpha$ -bis-(α -Naphthyl)- $\beta\beta\gamma$ -trichloro-*n*-butane.—The solid product obtained from butylchloral hydrate (24 g.), naphthalene (35.2 g.) and oleum (4%, 100 g.) at 45° for 3 hours, was washed well and crystallised from *n*-propyl alcohol. After several crystallisations, pure product of m.p. 196-98° was obtained (poor yield). (Found : Cl, 26.1. $C_{24}H_{18}Cl_3$ requires Cl, 25.7 per cent).

Attempt to dehydrohalogenate the pure compound (1 g.) by refluxing it with alcoholic potash (1 g.) for 4 hours was unsuccessful, the original compound being recovered unchanged. Direct oxidation with chromic acid in acetic was attempted but no definite product could be isolated.

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